

HYDROPTIM OPTIMIZATION TOOL

END USER MANUAL

22.12.2022

Table of contents

- 1. INTRODUCTION 2
- 2. USER 3
 - 1.1. HOW TO CREATE AN USER..... 3
 - 1.2. LOGIN 4
- 2. PROJECT..... 5
 - 2.1. HOW TO CREATE A PROJECT 5
 - 2.2. EDIT A PROJECT 5
 - 2.3. INACTIVATE A PROJECT..... 6
- 3. MODEL 7
 - 3.1. HOW TO ADD A MODEL 8
 - 3.2. HOW TO ADD ELEMENTS TO THE MODEL 8
 - 3.3. ACTIVATE AND INACTIVATE A MODEL10
 - 3.4. DUPLICATE A MODEL.....10
 - 3.5. DELETE A MODEL11
- 4. SCENARIO12
 - 4.1. HOW TO ADD A NEW SCENARIO12
 - 4.2. FILLING THE SCENARIO DATA INPUTS.....12
 - 4.3. RUNNING A SCENARIO SIMULATION.....13
 - 4.4. HOW TO READ THE OUTPUT OF A SIMULATION14
 - 4.5. DUPLICATE A SCENARIO15
 - 4.6. DELETE A SCENARIO15

1. INTRODUCTION

Hydroptim software is a web application developed with ReactJs on the client side or user interface and Java for business logic or Backend, it uses PostgreSQL as a base data and GAMS for the optimization.

This manual as it is for the final user, it will focus on the explanation of the user interface.

The main functionalities of the user interface are:

1. Creation the user and it will be able to login
2. Creation and edition of the project which can hold multiple models
3. Creation, edition, cloning and deletion a model
4. Design the model schema with graphical elements
5. Creation, edition, cloning and deletion a scenario
6. Run a scenario and visualisation the results of given scenario, also the ability to export them to excel format

2. USER

A user can have multiple projects, and in each project, he can add an unlimited number of models as needed for each use case. Also, he can create multiple scenarios for each model and run the simulation on them.

1.1. HOW TO CREATE AN USER

The screenshot shows the user registration interface. On the left is a blue sidebar with the HydroOptim logo (Ver. 1.0.4) and the Adasa logo (POWERED BY ADASA SISTEMAS). On the right is a white form with two tabs: 'LOGIN' and 'REGISTER'. The 'REGISTER' tab is selected. The form contains three input fields: 'User name', 'Password', and 'Confirm password'. Below these fields is a 'REGISTER' button.

As this application mains to be used inside an internal network the user creation form is together with login form in the login page, to create the user click on register tab and fill the form than click on register button

1.2. LOGIN

The screenshot displays the login interface for HydroOptim. On the left, a blue vertical banner features the HydroOptim logo (Ver. 1.0.4) at the top, a stylized 'adasa' logo in the center, and the text 'POWERED BY ADASA SISTEMAS' at the bottom. On the right, a white login form is shown with two tabs: 'LOGIN' (selected) and 'REGISTER'. Below the tabs are two input fields labeled 'User' and 'Password', and a 'LOGIN' button at the bottom.

If the user is not logged in or the session es expired, the app redirects the user to the login page where the user can either register or login

2. PROJECT

Active	NAME	DESCRIPTION	MODELS
●	Costa Brava Demo Site	Status of the case study today: Costa Brava is a touristic regio...	Total: 1 models ✖
●	Westland working version	Status of the case study today: Westland is a 90 km² region ...	Total: 7 models ✖

A project represents the location or site where the user wants to optimize the energy, environmental costs. It can have more than one model. The projects list page is the first where the user is directed when he logs in.

2.1. HOW TO CREATE A PROJECT

The form contains the following fields:

- Id**: Input field for the project ID.
- User**: Input field for the user name.
- Name**: Input field for the project name.
- Models**: Input field for the number of models.
- Description**: Large text area for the project description.

Click the button "+Project" in the bottom of the page of the projects list, then fill the form with the name and description of the project, and finally hit the save button.

2.2. EDIT A PROJECT

The form displays the following data for the 'Costa Brava Demo Site' project:

- Id**: 5588239
- User**: nextgen
- Name**: Costa Brava Demo Site
- Models**: 1
- Description**:

Status of the case study today:
Costa Brava is a touristic region located on the Mediterranean, characterized by high seasonal demand, frequent water scarcity episodes, also causing saltwater intrusion. It is also one of the first areas in the uptake of water reuse in Europe with 14 full-scale tertiary treatments that provide 4 hm³/year (2016) for agricultural irrigation, environmental uses, non-potable urban uses and, recently, indirect potable reuse.

Ambition until end of the project:
The Operator Consorci Costa Brava (CCB) aims to implement more flexible uses of reclaimed water. This includes sensitive ones such as indirect potable reuse through aquifer recharge and irrigation of private gardens. To do so, a modular tertiary treatment able to provide different fit-for-purpose water qualities will be evaluated. This will take place at Tossa de Mar WWTP where a pilot system will be added to the existing tertiary treatment to provide water for sensitive uses (private garden irrigation and/or indirect potable reuse). Feasibility of using end-of-life membranes from nearby desalination plants will be evaluated establishing another CE scheme. The local CoP together with the Catalan Water Authority (ACA) will identify current governance barriers and measures to overcome them to ensure continuation after the end of the project.

Ambition beyond the project: Results from NextGen should be directly applicable to most of the WWTP of the region, which are facing similar problems. At mid/long-term, total reclaimed water in the area.

If you need to edit the project you can do it by clicking on the name of the project in the breadcrumb trail. Then it will open a new page with the project data, that you can edit.

2.3. INACTIVATE A PROJECT

Active	NAME	DESCRIPTION	MODELS
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Costa Brava Demo Site	Status of the case study today: Costa Brava is a touristic regio...	Total: 1 models
<input type="checkbox"/>	Westland working version	Status of the case study today: Westland is a 90 km² region ...	Total: 7 models

To activate and deactivate a project, there is a circle in the left side of each row in the projects list. If you hit this button, it will change his colour to either red or green depend on state witch it was initially. Red mains that it deactivated and green mains that is active.

3. MODEL

Model is the water network schema of the project. If you click on an item of the projects list, it will bring you to the models page. Where you can see each model is presented by a card. In the bottom of the card there are these button icons:

1. Graph icon to access the schema editor of the model
2. List icon to access the scenarios list
3. Copy icon to copy the model
4. Delete icon to delete the model

3.1. HOW TO ADD A MODEL

Adding a new model to the project is done by clicking the button "+Model", that is at the bottom of the models list page. It will open a new page with the model schema editor.

3.2. HOW TO ADD ELEMENTS TO THE MODEL

To add an element to the model schema, you can drag an element from the list of the elements at the header of the editor to the till in the middle of the editor. So you can move it to place it wherever you need.

To delete an element from the schema, you need to select that element then click on button delete at the header of the editor

To edit the attributes of an element, select the element then at the bottom of the editor will appear a form where you can set/edit name, description and the colour of the selected item.

The element can be connected by a pipe represented by a dashed animated line. To connect two elements, you first click twice on the origin element then twice on the destiny element, an animated line will appear connecting two elements.

To delete the connection, just click on the line then hit the delete button at the header of the editor. Also, you can edit the properties of the pipe (line) the same way we do with the elements.

3.3. ACTIVATE AND INACTIVATE A MODEL

To activate and deactivate a model, there is a circle at top right of the model card, clicking that circle it change the state from active to inactive and vice versa.

3.4. DUPLICATE A MODEL

To create a copy of the model, click on the copy icon, it will appear a dialog asking if you want a deep or shallow copy of the model.

The deep copy will copy the schema of the model and all its scenarios with simulations results. The shallow copy will only copy the schema of the model without scenarios

3.5. DELETE A MODEL

To delete a model, click the delete icon, before the deletion start it will appear a confirmation dialog to confirm the deletion.

4. SCENARIO

Active	ID	Description	Created at	Resolved at	Infeasible	Unbounded	Errors	Total Energy	Total Cost		
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	5416853	Emergency proposal III	March 16, 2021 at 10:18:33	March 25, 2021 at 12:00:54	0	0	0	18368742.13999809	18368742.13999809		
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	5262257	Emergency proposal II	March 16, 2021 at 10:18:33	March 25, 2021 at 10:16:40	0	0	0	17814892.139359966	17814892.139359966		
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	5107661	Emergency proposal I	March 16, 2021 at 10:18:33	March 25, 2021 at 08:37:01	0	0	0	17263692.146998286	17263692.146998286		
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	4953065	Proposal Exceptionality	March 16, 2021 at 10:18:33	March 24, 2021 at 14:04:14	0	0	0	16328242.139998412	16328242.139998412		
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	4798469	Proposed Alert	March 16, 2021 at 10:18:33	March 24, 2021 at 11:35:33	0	0	0	16136117.13999831	16136117.13999831		
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	4643873	Emergency III	March 16, 2021 at 10:18:33	March 23, 2021 at 19:15:32	0	0	0	19253887.89998418	19253887.89998418		
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	4492277	Emergency II	March 16, 2021 at 10:18:33	March 23, 2021 at 17:41:29	0	0	0	18790471.089998312	18790471.089998312		
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	4334681	Emergency I	March 16, 2021 at 10:18:33	March 23, 2021 at 15:07:55	0	0	0	18327057.63999841	18327057.63999841		
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	4180085	Exceptionality	March 16, 2021 at 10:18:33	March 23, 2021 at 13:52:24	0	0	0	17631938.789998405	17631938.789998405		
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	4025489	Alarm	March 16, 2021 at 10:18:33	August 16, 2022 at 13:23:25	0	0	0	17168520.039998963	17168520.039998963		
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	3553130	Normality_tets	March 16, 2021 at 10:18:33	August 16, 2022 at 12:00:28	0	0	0	15803197.639998011	15803197.639998011		

The model can have a different scenario with different data. With the scenario you can set the data of the parameters of the model elements, run a simulation and consult the results of the simulation. To access to the scenarios list you have to click the list icon in the model card.

At the list page you can activate, deactivate, copy and delete a scenario.

4.1. HOW TO ADD A NEW SCENARIO

At the header of the footer of the model editor there is a "+SCENARIO" button at the right side to create a new scenario. If you need edit the existing one you just click at the scenario of the list then you will be redirected to the scenario edition page.

4.2. FILLING THE SCENARIO DATA INPUTS

First select the scenario from the list or add new one, it will open a new page looks like the image below

At the header of the page you can see the field for the general information of the scenario as description and the time horizon, then just below there is a tab where you can select elements you want to fill their inputs.

4.3. RUNNING A SCENARIO SIMULATION

At right of the header there is a button with the play icon, clicking it, it will start the simulation.

When the simulation start, it will show popup looks like a console where the output of the simulation will displayed.

4.4. HOW TO READ THE OUTPUT OF A SIMULATION

When the simulation finish, if every thing is ok you will see "INFEASIBLE", "UNBOUNDED" and "ERRORS" reading at the bottom of the scenario form are all green.

Also at the console should be 0 errors at the reading summary, if there is any error you can debug it from the console.

4.5. DUPLICATE A SCENARIO

To copy a scenario, go to the scenario list and at the right of each scenario there is button looks like a copy icon, if you click it, it will ask you if you want deep o shallow copying. The deep will copy scenario with inputs and results, but shallow will copy only the scenario without any data.

Active	ID	Description	Created at	Resolved at	Infeasible	Unbounded	Errors	Total Energy	Total Cost		
●	5416853	Emergency proposal III	March 16, 2021 at 10:18:33	March 25, 2021 at 12:00:54	0	0	0	18368742.13999899	18368742.13999899		
●	5262257	Emergency proposal II	March 16, 2021 at 10:18:33	March 25, 2021 at 10:16:40	0	0	0	17814892.139359966	17814892.139359966		
●	5107661	Emergency proposal I	March 16, 2021 at 10:18:33	March 25, 2021 at 08:37:01	0	0	0	17263692.146998286	17263692.146998286		
●	4953065	Proposal Exceptionality	March 16, 2021 at 10:18:33	March 24, 2021 at 14:04:14	0	0	0	16328242.139998412	16328242.139998412		
●	4798469	Proposed Alert	March 16, 2021 at 10:18:33	March 24, 2021 at 11:35:33	0	0	0	16136117.13999831	16136117.13999831		
●	4643873	Emergency III	March 16, 2021 at 10:18:33	March 23, 2021 at 19:15:32	0	0	0	19253887.189998418	19253887.189998418		

4.6. DELETE A SCENARIO

The deletion is done by the delete button, located at the right of the list. it will ask you if you want delete all or only the simulation which mean only the results of the simulation

ID	Description	Created at	Resolved at	Infeasible	Unbounded	Errors	Total Energy	Total Cost
5416853	Emergency proposal III	March 16, 2021 at 10:18:33	March 25, 2021 at 12:00:54	0	0	0	18368742.13999899	18368742.13999899
5262257	Emergency proposal II	March 16, 2021 at 10:18:33	March 25, 2021 at 10:16:40	0	0	0	17814892.139359966	17814892.139359966
5107661	Emergency proposal I	March 16, 2021 at 10:18:33	March 25, 2021 at 08:37:01	0	0	0	17263692.146998286	17263692.146998286
4953065	Proposal Exceptionality	March 16, 2021 at 10:18:33	March 24, 2021 at 14:04:14	0	0	0	16328242.139998412	16328242.139998412
4798469	Proposed Alert	March 16, 2021 at 10:18:33	March 24, 2021 at 11:35:33	0	0	0	16136117.13999831	16136117.13999831
4643873	Emergency III	March 16, 2021 at 10:18:33	March 23, 2021 at 19:15:32	0	0	0	19253887.189998418	19253887.189998418
4489277	Emergency II	March 16, 2021 at 10:18:33	March 24, 2021 at 14:04:14	0	0	0	18790471.089998312	18790471.089998312
4334681	Emergency I	March 16, 2021 at 10:18:33	March 25, 2021 at 08:37:01	0	0	0	18327057.63999841	18327057.63999841
4180085	Exceptionality	March 16, 2021 at 10:18:33	March 24, 2021 at 14:04:14	0	0	0	17631938.789998405	17631938.789998405
4025489	Alarm	March 16, 2021 at 10:18:33	March 24, 2021 at 11:35:33	0	0	0	17168520.039998963	17168520.039998963
3553130	Normality	March 16, 2021 at 10:18:33	March 23, 2021 at 10:28:35	0	0	0	15803197.639998011	15803197.639998011

DELETING THE SCENARIO

Are you sure you want to delete this scenario?
This action will delete basic configuration and related simulation!

CANCEL
DELETE ALL
ONLY THE SIMULATION